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Transformation of Regional Industry by the State Support Policy

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***Abstract:** The article examines the critical role of government policies in reshaping the industrial landscape of regions. It analyzes various state support mechanisms, such as financial incentives, regulatory frameworks, and infrastructure development, that facilitate industrial transformation. The article concludes with recommendations for policymakers to optimize support strategies, ensuring that regional industries can adapt to evolving economic challenges while promoting sustainable development. This work is relevant for researchers, policymakers, and industry leaders interested in the dynamics of industrial transformation and the implications of government action.*

***Key words:** conceptual frameworks, economic reforms, regional disparities, public welfare, economic parameters, age groups predominate, state budget, Modernizing regional industries.*

Introduction

In developing regional policies for industrial sectors, it is essential to consider several conceptual frameworks. Supporting regions through the promotion of growth in the manufacturing sector is crucial, as this sector is the primary source of new job creation. The government plays a vital role in facilitating the establishment and expansion of manufacturing enterprises, as well as in redirecting and improving them when necessary.

Global experiences in regional industrial policy are characterized by several common trends, including decentralization, inter-regional integration, environmental protection, and the enhancement of public welfare. To ensure stability in creating a macroeconomic balance, the implementation of regional policies by the government is of significant importance. The need for economic reforms in the regional industry arises from the fact that every country encompasses a diverse array of regions, each exhibiting distinct characteristics across various indicators.

Over time, the role of certain non-manufacturing factors in economic development may change, leading to conditions that are not consistently favorable for regional growth. Consequently, regional disparities significantly impact the overall economic development of a country. This disparity is

related, on one hand, to the unequal distribution of production resources across the nation's territory, and on the other hand, to the dynamic role of specific factors in economic growth.

As a result, each country may exhibit regions that are rich in natural resources but have low populations, as well as areas that are sufficiently endowed with both. Some regions may have already been developed or are in the process of being developed, while others experience population increases in some areas and decreases in others. Additionally, certain regions may have an aging population predominating, while in others, the proportion of older individuals is declining.

Research methodology

Firstly, studying the scientific and technical aspects of economic development has gained increasing importance and demand from the economy. The interplay between theory and economic practice is linked to the dynamics of economic parameters, quality of life, competitiveness, and economic security. It is essential to investigate and understand the role and essence of management within economic systems that have experienced varying degrees of development in productive forces and production relations throughout different historical periods. The significance of scientific and technical advancement and its impact is widely recognized as a unifying component among these perspectives.

Additionally, it is important to note the following regional characteristics:

- Areas rich in natural resources but with low populations.
- Regions adequately endowed with both resources and population.
- Areas that are already developed or in the process of development.
- Regions where population numbers are increasing in some areas while decreasing in others.
- Areas where older age groups predominate, contrasted with regions where their proportion is declining.

Results and discussion

To reduce regional disparities, the government implements regional policies, which represent a specific direction of economic regulation. This policy encompasses a set of measures aimed at achieving a balanced territorial production structure within the national economy. In formulating regional policies, it is essential to consider various conceptual frameworks. Supporting regions through the promotion of growth in the industrial production sector is crucial, as this sector generates the highest number of new jobs.

As a mechanism, the allocation of subsidies and grants to certain regions within the state budget is a primary strategy. Additionally, medium-term development forecasts and state programs for socio-economic development have been established for specific areas and sectors. The government has also issued decisions to provide incentives and favorable conditions for attracting and stimulating foreign investments, as well as for the development of small and private businesses in these regions.

However, in practice, the selection of problems for industrial product development is often limited to a list of "troubled" areas within the region's socio-economic development. A more effective approach would involve employing a scientifically grounded methodology to identify and prioritize issues that can unlock qualitatively new prospects for the region. This research proposes that government support for regional industrial development should be structured at three levels.

1st Level:

- Establishing digital governance based on big data within the regional industry.

2nd Level:

- Preserving and developing the aggregate of material resources;
- Modernizing regional industries;
- Planning the future development of the regional industrial complex;
- Attracting investments to regional industries;
- Facilitating the commercialization of products manufactured in regional industries.

3rd Level:

- Improving the territorial distribution and infrastructure of industry within the region;
- Protecting industrial ecology;
- Developing programs to increase the resource base for raw materials needed for production;
- Implementing industrial reforms in the region;
- Further diversifying industrial products;
- Attracting skilled personnel to the sector;
- Establishing mechanisms for investment attraction;
- Developing, adopting, and effectively implementing regional legislation to facilitate investment in the region;
- Systematically engaging with external investors to attract their investments to the region;
- Creating favorable conditions for employees of industrial enterprises;
- Enhancing the standard of living for the regional population;
- Improving the quality of life for the residents of the region.

Results and discussion

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, local scholars are conducting scientific research to provide a broader assessment of the industrial structure and analyze the socio-economic activities within this sector. Specifically, it is crucial to evaluate state support for the stabilization of industry, assess institutional changes, and explore new directions for development. Conceptual, theoretical, and practical research on managing scientific and technical progress is influenced by various factors. According to the institutional structure of the regional industry, the following aspects can be determined:

As indicated in the table, the new digital structure of the regional industry can be defined based on its institutional framework through the following aspects:

- The level of social-economic labor division and cooperation;
- The degree of independence of the state within the economy;
- The high scientific and technical potential of industry and personnel;
- The level of industrial development in the region and its territories;
- The production interconnections between groups "A" and "B" within industrial sectors;
- The level of social-economic labor productivity or social-economic efficiency;
- The identification of improvements in the material well-being and cultural standards of workers.

Conclusions

The informatization of the regional industry, along with ensuring protection and establishing safe and healthy working conditions, is a fundamental responsibility of specialists and all workers. In this context, the information structure necessary for protecting digital data during the production process is defined. The informatization and safeguarding of industrial structures serve as a guarantee for the protection of vital personal and societal interests against accidents and adverse events in hazardous production facilities and their consequences.

This involves the development, implementation, and optimization of ideological algorithms. Subsequently, a foundation is established for transformation, facilitating the process of collaboration among all stakeholders. Developers are responsible for ensuring the alignment of the technologies used. Furthermore, this leads to the emergence of a digital marketplace, which enables online connectivity between producers and consumers based on modern technologies.

References:

1. Перес, К. Технологические революции и финансовый капитал. Динамика пузырей и периодов расцветания / К. Перес ; пер. с англ. Ф.В. Маевского, науч. ред. пер. С.У. Глазев, В.Э. Дементев. – М.: Дело, 2011. –232 с.
2. Перес,К. Технологические революции и финансовый капитал.Динамика пузырей и периодов расцветания / К. Перес ; пер. с англ.Ф.В. Маевского, науч. ред. пер. С.У. Глазев, В.Э. Дементев. – М.: Дело, 2011. –232 с
3. Перру Ф. Экономическое пространство: теория и приложения // Пространственная экономика. №2. 2007 – С. 124-134;
4. Райзберг, Б.А. Современный экономический словарь. - 6-е изд.,перераб. и доп. / Б.А. Райзберг, Л.Ш. Лозовский, Е.Б. Стародубцева. - М.:ИНФРА-М, 2017.- 512 с
5. Разработка иерархической многокритериальной процедуры оценки качества экспертов/ Путивцева Н.П., Игрунова С.В., Бекетова Е.Ю., Капитан С.А. // Научный результат. 2016. Выпуск №1 (1). С 39-47.
6. Рамо, Дж. К. Седмое чувство. Как прогнозировать и управлять изменениями в цифровую эпоху / Дж. К. Рамо. – М. : Изд-во: «Эксмо», 2017. – 336 с
7. Растворцева С.Н. Инновационный путь изменения траектории предшествующего развития экономики региона. // Экономика региона. 2020. – Т.16, вып.1 – С. 28-42